

**HOLISTIC ON THE BASIS OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY
"STEAM",THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF SYSTEMATIZED
KNOWLEDGE-GIVING**

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Annotation:In this article, Steam is integrated based on educational technology, theoretical parables of systematized knowledge-giving have been studied.

Keywords: Education technology, personality-oriented education, science integration, interdisciplinary interconnection, STEAM education technology, career orientation, technologist-engineering thought.

Integrated into the world community, our country the process of the society of the social and economic changes in the life of a new generation of professionals push the development of necessary theoretical knowledge, it must possess the skills and qualifications to the new requirements is being produced. This is the first scientific knowledge that requires a lot of modern technologies, the country is wide spread , and secondly, the complexity of work and changes in the teaching process of the results is relevant.

The same, in the same context of the republic of Uzbekistan new “on education” of the law (the year 2020 (September 23) and the “National program for training” at takidlanganidek , the main purpose of the education organization – in the community that can provide rise to the level of social development advanced countries of the world, which contributes to the strong-willed, independent-minded, positive to have a quality, educated, prepared and qualified personnel organized to convey the process of the formation of [1,2].

“...Twenty-first century leaders who tsivilizasiyasiga scientific and technical capabilities in the process of his intellectual analysis, synthesis, evaluation, intellectual and creative abilities as well as cultivate your career in it and if

moslanuvchan better than others is the gift of work - this was written almost 30 years ago, the prophecy of firik-comments which put a modern professionals to prepare very specific requirements are identified [3].

As noted in the world declaration on higher education for the xxi century: “...the building the critical mass of qualified and widely educated people not to be able to stand adekvat higher education and research institutions could not have been real and ensuring sustainable development in any country...” [4].

Therefore also has a great development in the future, fair legal, democratic government and the free development of creative thinking of young who aim to build a civil society in our country, the desire to create their own news, and a desire to rise to the level of humanism and one of the main events in the way of the ultimate goal of the education system should be considered. The creativity of students in the teaching process of teachers of higher educational institutions, to seek, to mushohada, modern pedagogical and information technologies aimed at the development of logical thinking, which includes the use of interactive methods according to the purpose .

To resolve this task using the rich spiritual world of the people of the achievements of science and innovation activities, widely base and universal, the concentration of the following times traditional national culture, economic and of science, engineering and technology on the latest achievements of building a system based perfect education, the society for the active-minded, imaginative and innovative ideas, supporting them in practice to prepare qualified specialists in today's society because it has the urgent need for rapid development during the period of active role-minded, imaginative and innovative ideas in practice required of qualified professionals that are effective in supporting them. This, in turn, innovasiyalar the education process, and requires the introduction of modern teaching interactive and creative methods [5].

The above idea-thinking come out this article in higher education, natural-steam

technology, which is one of the exact sciences to undergraduate students on the basis of texnolgiyalaridan modern education, higher education in science, education, production, taking into account competition, the essence of the science of physics science, technology, arts and mathematics integration engineering given to approach - professional referral –based profession that was in the future to holistic, is systematized.

The mutual connection of the subject of education is one of the features of the content, and the coordination of educational programs in the process of education tizimlilik principle appears in [6].

Didactic conditions for the mutual connection of the subject, that is, it put on, not only on the educational process and systematized reader-solid knowledge that increases student by mark proficient readers read of interests, theories, ensures that the scientific concept would be in a relationship with. As a result, not only the knowledge, it becomes apparent, generalized and creates the opportunity to apply them in practice. So along with the mutual connection allows the effective use of the subject at the time of the study [7].

The implementation of the mutual connection of the subject is didactic conditions, first of all to the content of the educational material and scientific concepts, laws and theories in order to reveal the essence, secondly in the education of their methods (tracking, educational experiences, and others), as well as the students moved from one science to another and support and targeted series-rdiagnosis is included in[8].

Steam-powered technology on education as the analysis of the literature shows, this science education, technology integration given to technologists-thought muxandislik utilized on the basis of theoretical knowledge, master the skills, qualifications and compensations with life, with practice, will go far towards the development of complex with the production method provided by the time the students had surrounded us, and the universe are constantly in motion micro makro

holistic, integral, integrity mean fahmlab. it will help you to figure out.

Steam technology proficient students on the basis of theoretical knowledge of mathematics and other exact sciences from the basis of science, engineering, design, technology, tied as they are, create their own projects and the device will go to realize the essence of the work, holistic, systematized scientific knowledge, skills, qualifications and opportunities will be able to go.

STEAM-in an unconventional way is to read the scientific theory of the natural sciences, technology, engineering, arts and mathematics teaching is in harmony with the style.

Steam-powered technology unlike traditional education does not separate from knowledge, based on the integration of science mastering brings.

Steam - powered technology education students ill-kompetentsiyalarini is focused on the development of technical directions.

Abbreviation of Steam	STEAM content
S	in science-science. Students in the sciences of knowledge, skills, qualifications and skills development on the basis of scientific compensation
T	Technology –technology students in the sciences of knowledge, skills, qualifications and development of modern technologies based on kompetentsiyalarni
E	engineering-engineering. Students in the field of engineering knowledge, skills, qualifications and development kompetentsiyalarni
A	– art. The outlook for students in the field of art and culture, expand their knowledge, skills, qualifications and development kompetentsiyalarni

M	mathematics – mathematics. Students in the field of mathematics knowledge, skills, qualification and development kompetentsiyalarni
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Steam-powered technology in the teaching of graduate education sciences on the basis of the basis of non-standard conditions to solve problems arising in education at all stages of the engineering ability and creativity that is necessary in mastering the skills of labor and the development of independent life, an independent life and outlook step in to the shape of bazaviy kompetensiya which is needed. Along with this, the quality of the teachers and scientists of the whole world new and modern techniques and technologies to prepare personnel possessing increased from day to day without steam, which implies that the demand for personnel, engineer-education of the application program in particular is significant.

STEAM (Science – natural sciences, technology – technology, engineering – engineering Art – art, mathematics and mathematics) education through the introduction of students to the integration of science increases the level of literacy is built. On the basis of international experience approach to learning and education to steam education system today the introduction of the attitude changes. Students-students practical skills oraqli to pay attention to will, creativity, adaptation to cooperate with others in achieving greater interoperability develop and learn. During the period of educational and occupational development in all areas of science today on steam new look without understanding clearly the reduction specialists to prepare technological, 'll muxandislik science and mathematics, and will not be implemented. These teaching science in physics with a number of higher education graduates in scientific and technological literacy, and engineering skills compensations the formation of modern technical systems and technology at the professional level at

the same time, the use of technical management system allows you to design and mastering. The main mechanism in the system of continuous education of physics integrasion performs the function of natural, scientific-technical, technological and humanitarian sciences of the body of knowledge within the framework of meta-level teaches the practical aspects of science and higher education will help to strengthen to apply. On the basis of modern requirements of graduate study in the science of physics in the process of mastering the technology of production through the understanding, application, control, and improvement assessment, design, research, management has begun to form. To choose the proper technology is an effective and non-standard thinking and skills of doing business through the formation of new products, services and work can create new methods of influence. That is necessary to master the professional skills of the profession through different independent to the right choice in life, to work, to master new skills to perfection, doing independent work and practical activities that change on your own and quickly to achieve economic, political and social conditions in a flexible, independent education specialists will educate prepared to take in ambiguous situations.

Thus,the STEAM-educational technology on the analysis of the literature shows that educational technologists on the basis of this technology from science foundation-thought muxandislik utilized on the basis of theoretical knowledge,possessed the skills, qualifications and kompetensiyalar with life,with practice,will go far towards the development of complex with the production method provided by the time the students had surrounded us,and the universe are constantly in motion micro makro holistic, integral, integrity mean to figure out fahmlab and the conclusion helps.

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